

MECHANICAL BEHAVIOR OF SILANE GRAFTED GRAPHENE NANOPATELETS / SILICONE RUBBER COMPOSITES

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1 Introduction

A uniform dispersion of has been considered as a crucial issue in the fabrication of graphene based polymer composites [1]. A common method for inducing well dispersion in solution or polymer matrix is to graft suitable functional groups on the surface of graphene nanoplatelets. In silicone rubber system, silane coupling agents with a short segment in organofunctional group, such as 3-aminopropyltriethoxysilane (APTES) [2] or γ -aminopropyltriethoxysilane (KH550) [3], are often used for the functionalization of graphene nanoplatelets. Although those silane coupling agents provide an improved dispersion for silane grafted graphene in the silicone rubber matrix and further enhanced their electrical conductivity [4], their mechanical properties is still insufficient for the application of compliant electrodes. In this study, a silane coupling agent with a medium segment organofunctional group, diethoxy(methyl)octylsilane, was used for the chemical grafting on the graphene nanoplates. The effects of graphene contents, silanized functionalization on the mechanical behavior of graphene nanoplatelets/silicone rubber composites were also explored.

2 Experimental

The silane grafted graphene nanoplatelets was synthesized by the chemical functionalization of graphene oxide. Multilayered graphene nanoplatelets with 20-40 layers, purchased from Anstron Material Incorporation, were first modified using a hummer method in order to create the oxygen contained functional groups on the surface of graphene nanoplatelets. The chemical functionalization of graphene nanoplatelets was carried out by the chemical grafting of Diethoxy(methyl)octylsilane. The silane grafted graphene oxides were reduced by the hydrazine solution at 80°C and further dried at

50°C overnight. Fig. 1 shows the SEM image of the chemical grafted graphene nanoplatelets. As shown, most products had a flocculent morphology and an obvious agglomeration was also observed. After the chemical functionalization of graphene nanoplatelets, the silicone rubber composite is fabricated by adding silanized graphene nanoplatelets into RTV silicone system with different contents of 0.5wt%-5wt%. The graphene nanoplatelets/ silicone rubber solutions were prepared in high speed shearing mixing and cured at 130°C for 30min.

Fig. 1 SEM image of the chemical grafted graphene nanoplatelets.

3 Results and Discussion

Fig. 2 shows that the XPS spectrum of silane grafted graphene nanoplatelets. As indicated in Fig.2 (a), four obvious peaks with different binding energies could be found from the deconvoluted C1s peak, which are the 284.6eV for C-C (sp²), 285.1eV for C-C (sp³), 285.8eV for epoxy groups (-C-O) and 288eV for carboxylic groups (-COO-). The formation of epoxy groups and carboxylic groups are due to the strong oxidation at the surface of the graphene nanoplatelets during the hummer process. As shown in Fig.2 (b), two deconvoluted peaks from Si2p peak are observed to confirm the formation of silane grafting. The first component at 102.3eV is

assigned to Si-O-Si bonds of a siloxane network formed between the silane molecules at the surface of graphene nanoplatelets. The second one at 102.9eV is characteristic of Si-O-C bonds.

Fig. 2 XPS spectrum of silane grafted graphene nanoplatelets: (a) C1s spectra; (b) Si2p spectra.

Fig.3 represents the TGA results of the silane grafted graphene nanoplatelets under an argon atmosphere. Two clear stages in the curve of weight loss were found when raising the heating temperature, and the final residual mass of 59.69% was found at 800°C. The first stage of weight loss around 100°C could be considered as the removal of adsorbed water. On the other hand, a dramatic decrease of 30.37% in weight loss between 100°C to 600°C was corresponded to the pyrolysis of the silane grafted on the graphene nanoplatelets.

Fig.3 TGA results of the silane grafted graphene nanoplatelets under a argon atmosphere.

Fig. 4 shows the tensile strength of graphene nanoplatelets/silicone rubber composites as function of the graphene contents. As indicated in Fig. 4, only a slight increase in as-received graphene nanoplatelets samples were found when graphene content was 1wt%, and the tensile strength of 2.23 MPa could be obtained. On the other hand, a dramatic increase could be observed in the silane

grafted graphene nanoplatelets samples since graphene contents is up to 1wt%, and the maximum tensile strength was achieved to 5.71MPa. Comparison of the tensile strength of as-received samples and silane grafted samples using a graphene content of 1wt% indicates that an increase of 184% on tensile strength for silane grafted graphene nanoplatelets samples could be obtained. The reason could be attributed to a better dispersion for the silane grafted graphene nanoplatelets, which resulted in the reinforcement on the interface between the graphene and silicone rubber matrix.

Fig. 4 Tensile strength of graphene nanoplatelets/silicone rubber composites as function of the graphene contents.

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